

Interactions of the Ca²⁺ modulating and transporting ORAI1 and SPCA2 promote oncogenic activities

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Changes in the cytosolic calcium (Ca²⁺) concentration ([Ca²⁺]_c) can induce signaling pathways that regulate a broad range of cellular events, including those important in tumorigenesis. A recent study has characterized a new mechanism of constitutive Ca²⁺ signaling that involves the Ca²⁺ store-operated channel ORAI1 and ATP-powered Ca²⁺ pumps.

One diagnostic feature of breast cancers is the formation of micro-calcifications that can be seen on mammograms, suggesting that deregulation of Ca²⁺ signaling might be a characteristic of this type of cancer. To investigate the underlying mechanisms through which this might occur, Feng *et al.* examined the expression of secretory pathway Ca²⁺-ATPase (SPCA) family members in various human breast cancer cell lines and non-malignant cells [1]. They found that the levels of SPCA1 were similar in all cells examined, whereas SPCA2 was up-regulated in breast cancer cells compared with non-malignant cells. Of note, while SPCA1 is ubiquitously expressed, SPCA2 is limited to gastrointestinal, genitourinary and nervous systems, as well as mammary and salivary glands [2,3]. Knockdown of SPCA2 in MCF-7 cells (a human breast adenocarcinoma cell line) led to inhibition of proliferation, reduction in ability to form colonies in soft agar, and reduced tumour formation in a xenograft mouse model. By contrast, overexpression of SPCA2 in a non-malignant mammary epithelial cell line, MCF-10A, increased proliferation conferring colony-form to these cells. Are these oncogenic activities of SPCA2 mediated through Ca²⁺ signaling? The authors found that intracellular Ca²⁺ levels in SPCA2-knockdown MCF-7 cells were reduced compared with control MCF-7 cells, and that overexpression of SPCA2 led to increased basal Ca²⁺ concentration, strongly suggesting that up-regulation of SPCA2 in breast cancer cells leads to increased intracellular Ca²⁺ and thus tumorigenic capacity. Is the increased Ca²⁺ concentration observed in breast cancer cells dependent on the known Ca²⁺-pumping ability of SPCA2? To test this, the authors created a mutant version of SPCA2 with impaired Ca²⁺-ATPase activity and, surprisingly, expression of this SPCA2 mutant increased [Ca²⁺]_c in HEK293 cells with a consequent higher growth rate of MCF-10A cells on soft agar, similar to the effects of wild-type SPCA2. These

results suggest that SPCA2 can induce Ca²⁺ influx independently of its ATPase function.

The authors found also that SPCA2 localizes to the plasma membrane in MCF-7 cells, suggesting that it might interact with plasma membrane Ca²⁺ channels to mediate Ca²⁺ entry. Interestingly, although they observed that SPCA2-mediated Ca²⁺ entry was independent of the Ca²⁺ content of endoplasmic reticulum (ER), they found that SPCA2 interacted with the store-operated Ca²⁺ channel ORAI1. SPCA2 co-immunoprecipitated with ORAI1, and SPCA2-ORAI1 complexes could be found at the plasma membrane, indicating that ORAI1 regulates SPCA2-mediated Ca²⁺ influx in breast cancer cells. Consistent with this, ORAI1 knockdown in MCF-7 cells reduced basal Ca²⁺ concentration, proliferation, colony formation and tumour formation in a xenograft model, similar to the phenotypes observed on SPCA2 knockdown. Moreover, ORAI1 knockdown in MCF-10A cells overexpressing SPCA2 reversed the tumorigenic abilities conferred by SPCA2 overexpression, confirming that oncogenic pathways are promoted by interactions between ORAI1 and SPCA2 in breast cancer cells. Importantly, SPCA2-induced elevation of [Ca²⁺]_c is correlated with constitutive activation of RAS-ERK signaling pathway, by eliciting ERK1/2 phosphorylation and Cyclin D1 expression [1]. This relationship of Ca²⁺ and signaling cascade is emerging in the regulation of membrane trafficking, which is at the base of protein secretion.

Of interest, the other member of the SPCA family, SPCA1 (localizing mainly on the Golgi apparatus [4]) has been proved to be the main trigger of the peri-Golgi [Ca²⁺]_c fundamental for intra-Golgi trafficking [5]. The temporary increased [Ca²⁺]_c in the peri-Golgi area recruit Ca²⁺-sensing protein/enzymes (eg. cPLA2) on the Golgi membranes that become remodeled in their composition and conformation to allow the trafficking [6,7]. These considerations reinforce the concept that Ca²⁺ and signaling cascade are strictly related in regulating the membrane trafficking, as it has been proved for the ER-to-Golgi membranes [8]. However, Ca²⁺ regulated from SPCAs doesn't come from the ER, where SPCAs don't localize at all. This open new scenario on the role of Ca²⁺ stored in different organelles, and their role

on triggering the Ca^{2+} -mediated signaling. Explore the oncogenic signaling pathway must be considered of main interest also in other non-related SPCA2 pathologies, where however Ca^{2+} signaling is the keystone for the carcinogenic process. The results of Feng *et al.* [1] highlight SPCA2 and ORAI1 as potential targets for therapeutic intervention in breast cancer. Interestingly, other pathologies like oral cancer, and in particular salivary gland, one of the most common, where SPCA2 is normally overexpressed [9], could be another beneficiary of potential drugs working on regulating the SPCA2 activity. Furthermore, identification of the pathophysiological role of Ca^{2+} signaling highlights clinical implications in prognosis and treatment of oral malignancy.

Further studies need to explore the role of SPCA2 in regulating the Ca^{2+} signaling that could be the keystone to explain many, if not all, cancers in tissues expressing SPCA2. Thus, using different cellular approaches will be fundamental to better understand the labyrinth of the Ca^{2+} signaling that is finely tuned. Even if SPCA2 was only recently investigated as trigger for the Ca^{2+} signaling it could be the most promising, and the presented work of Feng *et al.* [1] is just the first brick in the wall. The game just began.

References

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